

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TOURISM DIRECTIONS)

Yuldasheva Dilfuza Kodirovna

a lecturer of Namangan state university, English philology faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7315614>

Abstract. *Speaking is the key to communication. By considering what good speakers do, what speaking tasks can be used in class, and what specific needs learners report, teachers can help learners to improve their speaking and overall oral competency. Teaching speaking is a very important part of second language learning. The ability to communicate in a second language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in school and success later in every phase of life. These activities make students more active in the learning process and at the same time make their learning more meaningful and fun for them. In this article we can discuss information about methodology for developing students' communicative competence in English (on the example of Tourism directions).*

Keywords: *Speaking skill, communicative competence, methods, students, English, tourism, development, benefits, guiders.*

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TOURISM DIRECTIONS)

Аннотация. *Речь – это ключ к общению. Принимая во внимание то, что делают хорошие ораторы, какие задания на говорение можно использовать в классе и о каких конкретных потребностях учащиеся сообщают, учителя могут помочь учащимся улучшить их разговорную речь и общую устную речь. Обучение разговорной речи является очень важной частью изучения второго языка. Способность ясно и эффективно общаться на втором языке способствует успеху учащегося в школе и успеху в дальнейшем на каждом этапе жизни. Эти мероприятия делают учащихся более активными в процессе обучения и в то же время делают их обучение более значимым и увлекательным для них. В данной статье мы можем обсудить информацию о методике развития коммуникативной компетенции студентов на английском языке (на примере туристического направления).*

Ключевые слова: *Умение говорить, коммуникативная компетенция, методы, студенты, английский язык, туризм, развитие, льготы, гиды.*

Speaking is a fundamental language skill. It is the primary way in which we communicate information. As guiders, however, we must be mindful that speaking involves more than simply using words to articulate what we are thinking, and there is more at play than simply asking students to say the words that they know.

Communicative competence - being a 'good speaker' requires a range of skills beyond accurate grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation, though these are the basic building blocks that enable a message to be understood. An effective communicator chooses the words they use, and the way in which they speak to different people in different situations, whether that is ordering a sandwich at a snack bar or giving a keynote speech at an academic event. The skills involved in how we interact with others in different ways are called communicative competencies: teachable skills which frame the language used in interaction in different settings.

As for tourism students, speaking as a language skill involves these competencies much more than it requires accuracy of language, so when we talk about ‘teaching speaking’, we are talking about something different from grammar or vocabulary practice. Speaking can be used to practice new language (as is common in question-answer tasks or role-plays held after specific language instruction, but this kind of activity may not teach the skill of speaking itself. Teaching speaking for tourism students as a set of competencies just as we can instruct, present and practice specific grammar features to students, the component competencies which make up speaking as a pure language skill can also be broken down and presented systematically. Some useful language sub-skills which can be turned into practice activities are:

- ❖ Avoiding repetition
- ❖ Responding appropriately while listening
- ❖ Turn-taking techniques
- ❖ Politeness
- ❖ Circumlocution (talking around unknown words using known language)
- ❖ Extending ideas

Notice that none of these sub-skills make specific reference to grammar, vocabulary or pronunciation, though obviously these are necessary for students to communicate what they want to say. In order to bring the focus onto these competencies, it is therefore advisable to lead speaking tasks on topics that are familiar to students, and using language that is within their ability. Taking the strain of new language out of speaking activities allows students to focus on the pure sub-skills listed above. This is similar to the way in which native speakers are ‘trained’ for public speaking or assertiveness in social situations: as native speakers, they are comfortable with the structure of their own language, but want to develop other skills which go along with that.

How can we teach tourism students for speaking competences through some kinds of modern methods? Many of these features of speaking fall into the category of discourse – the organization and style of a message as it is delivered in different situations. When teaching speaking in a given context, think about how people actually speak in that situation. Find recordings of people interacting in restaurants, banks, or wherever your lesson will be set, and think about the functional steps of the interaction as it happens.

Speaking lessons often tie in pronunciation and grammar which are necessary for effective oral communication. Or a grammar or reading lesson may incorporate a speaking activity. Either way, your students will need some preparation before the speaking task. This includes introducing the topic and providing a model of the speech they are to produce. A model may not apply to discussion-type activities, in which case students will need clear and specific instructions about the task to be accomplished. Then the students will practice with the actual speaking activity.

These activities may include imitating (repeating), answering verbal cues, interactive conversation, or an oral presentation. Here are some ideas to keep in mind as you plan your speaking activities. As much as possible, the content should be practical and usable in real-life situations. Avoid too much new vocabulary or grammar, and focus on speaking with the language the students have.

Tourism students will probably find that most interaction that you listen to is quite formulaic and predictable, so can be used as a structure for the dialogues that you present and

practice in class, only with the organization and ordering of the speech as the focus of the class rather than the specific language used. Taking an opposite approach, think of situations where the above list of competencies is common. For example: we often use circumlocution when we are talking about complex, technical subjects, like when we describe a problem we are having with a gas cooker, car engine or plumbing; we may not know the exact name of the part which is not working, but we can still communicate it to a gas fitter, mechanic or plumber. This is a useful life skill, and one which can be used to harness second-language speaking for language learners.

Also, tourism students, as with grammar and vocabulary, we can incorporate these target competencies into standard formats of lessons – we can present the feature of speech through an audio or video task, and then ask students to practice applying the feature in a restricted task. Gapped dialogues, ordering lines in a script, or choosing the best alternative from three different responses in a conversation, for example. Again, as long as the learners are playing with language they already know, their ‘discourse brains’ will be more engaged and they will have more focus on the competencies they are learning. Free speaking tasks should be exactly that: student-student interaction which does not have too many limitations. Give tourism students a topic or situation and ask them to script out a typical interaction in that situation and accounting to their subject which is tourism.

Teachers can come out with interesting, authentic and essential topics that students can discuss or talk about especially in the target language. The related topics should be easy and understandable. As a start ESL teachers can relate the topics with students' interests before moving to serious topics like national issues or the world politics. Lastly, in class or group discussions, whatever the aim is, the students should always be encouraged to ask questions, paraphrase ideas, express support, check for clarification, and so on.

In this activity, students are supposed to be working in pairs. One student will have the information that other partner does not have and the partners will share their information. Information gap activities serve many purposes such as solving a problem or collecting information. Also, each partner plays an important role because the task cannot be completed if the partners do not provide the information the others need. These activities are effective because everybody has the opportunity to talk extensively in the target language.

Brainstorming. On a given topic, students can produce ideas in a limited time. Depending on the context, either individual or group brainstorming is effective and learners generate ideas quickly and freely. The good characteristics of brainstorming is that the students are not criticized for their ideas so students will be open to sharing new ideas.

Storytelling. Students can briefly summarize a tale or story they heard from somebody beforehand, or they may create their own stories to tell their classmates. Story telling fosters creative thinking. It also helps students express ideas in the format of beginning, development, and ending, including the characters and setting a story has to have. Students also can tell riddles or jokes. For instance, at the very beginning of each class session, the teacher may call a few students to tell short riddles or jokes as an opening.

Interviews. Students can conduct interviews on selected topics with various people. It is a good idea that the teacher provides a rubric to students so that they know what type of questions they can ask or what path to follow, but students should prepare their own interview questions. Conducting interviews with people gives students a chance to practice their speaking ability not only in class but also outside and helps them becoming socialized. After interviews, each student

can present his or her study to the class. Moreover, students can interview each other and "introduce" his or her partner to the class.

Finally, be aware that although your learners have been focusing on these great features of spoken communication, they have not yet had the opportunity to fully apply these until they have spoken totally freely, without a script, or notes to work from (after all, native speakers don't carry scripts around with them to use in sandwich bars, though they do have an 'expected script' in their mind which informs their use of language), by participating in a speaking event with another student or students. The same dialogue that was used in free practice can be repeated, though with different participants to ensure spontaneity and flexibility with language. Only then can you say that students have truly applied what they are learning by the end of the class.

Conclusion, when planning a speaking skills lesson, in order to improve our students' speaking skill who major in tourism, we have to be aware that using language in speech is not necessarily practice of speaking as a language skill. Developing the range of competencies that make 'a good speaker' takes focus on the ways that we speak to different people, and the ways we construct what we are saying. This is independent from the grammar and vocabulary we use in real life, so should be kept separate from pure language input in the language classroom. Speaking is a crucial part of the tourism. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance, therefore, recent pedagogical research on teaching students conversation has provided some parameters for developing objectives and techniques.

REFERENCES

1. Brown and Yule. 1999. *Teaching the Spoken Language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Murcia, Marriane Celce. 2001. *Teaching English as A Second or Foreign Language*. United States: Heinle and Heinle Thomson.
3. Nunan, D. and Clarice Lamb. 1996. *The Self-directed Teacher: Managing the learning process*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
4. Nunan, David., 2000. *Language Teaching Methodology. A Textbook for Teachers*. Sydney: Longman.
5. Widdowson, H. G. 1978. *Teaching Language as Communication*. Oxford: Oxford University
6. University
1. Yuldasheva D.K. Peculiarities of teaching English based on a communicative approach to students of the Tourism department. *International Journal of Pedagogics*. 2022. Vol.02/issue 10 (68-71).